

Fourier Series with Binomial Coefficients of Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper presents a computational technique for developing a trigonometric series with binomial coefficients defined in combinatorial geometric series. This trigonometric series is extended as a Fourier series with binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to compute the multiple summations of a geometric series [1-9], a new idea stimulated his mind to create a new type of geometric series. As a result, a combinatorial geometric series [10-18] was developed with new idea of binomial coefficients.

2. System of Binomial Coefficients

The combinatorial geometric series is derived from the multiple summations of a geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial geometric series [18-25] refers to the binomial coefficient [26-40].

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i,$$

$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ denotes the combinatorial geometric series and V_n^r the binomial coefficient,

where, $V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r)}{r!}$ and integers $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$.

Any binomial coefficient, say V_n^r , can be expressed as a sum of series of binomial coefficients as follows:

$$V_n^r = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r-1} \Rightarrow V_n^{r+1} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r. \quad \text{Also, } V_n^{r-1} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r-2}.$$

For example,

$$V_4^3 = V_0^2 + V_1^2 + V_2^2 + V_3^2 + V_4^2,$$

where $V_0^2 + V_1^2 + V_2^2 + V_3^2 + V_4^2 = 1 + 3 + 6 + 10 + 15 = 35$ and

$$V_4^3 = \frac{(4+1)(4+2)(4+3)}{3!} = 35.$$

3. Fourier Series with Binomial Coefficients

A Fourier series is a way of representing a periodic function $f(t)$ as an infinite sum of sine and cosine functions.

The sine and cosine functions are given below:

Angular velocity (ω) is a displacement (θ) per unit time, i. e. $\omega = \frac{\theta}{t}$, where t denotes time.

$$\text{If } \theta = 2\pi, \text{ then } t = T \text{ (time period) and } \omega = \frac{2\pi}{T}.$$

$A \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t\right)$ and $B \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{T} t\right)$ are sine and cosine functions, where A and B are coefficients.

Let us develop a finite trigonometric series with binomial coefficients defined in combinatorial geometric series.

$$S = \sum_{i=0}^n (V_i^p \sin \theta + V_i^q \cos \theta). \text{ If } \theta = 0^\circ, S = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^q = V_n^{q+1} \text{ and if } \theta = 90^\circ, \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^p = V_n^{p+1}.$$

The infinite trigonometric series given below is the Fourier series with binomial coefficients defined in the combinatorial geometric series.

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(V_{a_n}^{p_n} \sin\left(n \frac{2\pi}{T} t\right) + V_{b_n}^{q_n} \cos\left(n \frac{2\pi}{T} t\right) \right).$$

4. Conclusion

In this article, we have developed a trigonometric series and the Fourier series with binomial coefficients defined in the combinatorial geometric series. These trigonometric series can be used as an application in science and technology.

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